

PROPOSAL FOR MORE EFFICIENT HEAT RECOVERY FROM BLACK LIQUOR IN BATCH COOKING PROCESS

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Abstract

Decrease in energy bill of every company or factory can be achieved by more efficient heat recuperation. Paper industry belongs to industries with high energy demand per unit production, due to energy intense process like wood chips cooking, pulp and paper drying, cooking chemicals recovery etc. This work deals with the hot water production during the cooking process in a real batch cooker. We strive to analyze the current situation with respect to heat recuperation efficiency and produced hot water utilization. It is shown that current fluctuations in hot water productions can be lessened by implementation of simple measures aimed at a moderate change in black liquor storage tanks level control. Thereby the regular peak overflow of produced hot water to warm water tank could be minimized and net heat flux available in hot water would be increased. Further improvement can be achieved with introduction of cooling water inlet temperature control, aimed at maximization of hot water production and stabilization of its temperature. The conservative estimate of net heat saving of 1.5 MW could be translated into fuel savings by utilization of the extra heat for boiler feedwater preheating or in Bleaching process.

Introduction

Pulp and paper (P&P) industry traditionally belongs to energy-intensive industrial branches. An excessive energy report prepared for the USA Department of Energy (DoE) by several American institutions estimates the 2002 annual energy demand of this industry solely in the USA as nearly 2500 PJ¹. Another one prepared by Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovations Research, dealing with cost effectiveness and electric energy consumption in industry generally, identifies the P&P industry as the second most energy intense industry in the Europe². Its total annual European energy demand amounts to nearly 900 PJ in 2007, contributing with over 6 % to the total annual industrial one in Europe. We see a comparable situation on our national level as well.

Energy saving possibilities in this and similar types of industry attracted quite a lot attention in the last decades. Focus has been put on improved use of excess (waste) heat from industrial processes^{3,4}, reducing the fuel consumption by improved heat recovery^{5,6} and electric energy consumption by the use of modern technologies^{7,8}, exploiting the cogeneration potential^{3,5,9} and recognizing the role of industrial facilities as perspective suppliers of heat for district heating^{6,10}. Several recent studies also deal with batch processes, as they still can be found in many production technologies, aiming at optimization of heat recovery from such processes^{11,12}. A study on waste energy usage shows several examples of possible measures, implementing already known and well-proven procedures and technologies that, if fully exploited, would lead to considerable savings in primary energy consumption³. Viswanathan et al. state that opportunities for heat recovery from chemical, refining, petrochemical and wood industry, from drying processes and from metals industry represent roughly 10 to 15 % of energy consumed in those industries and processes and amount to around 1400 PJ annually solely in the U.S⁴. Optimization of heat recovery from batch chemical processes is the main aim of recent publication by de Boer et al.¹². They propose a heat recovery system from a polymerization process operated batchwise in a series of independent chemical reactors that consists of stratified water tank and mechanical vapour recompression unit (a heat pump). Resulting payback period depends strongly on the electric energy price used to drive the heat pump.

P&P industry typically employs continuous processes, however the wood chips digesting (cooking) is traditionally performed batchwise. Continuous cooking technology exists already but is not yet very widespread¹³. Cooking process is exotherm, however it additionally consumes large quantities of middle pressure steam. Heat from steam plus that from chemical reaction is then cascaded to lower temperatures, partly serving for cooking liquor and fresh wood chips preheat, part of it is lost to the environment and quite a large portion of it transforms to heat content of hot water that is produced in this process and exported to other production units^{13,14}. Due to the cyclical nature of this process, the amount of heat available for hot water production varies considerably. This in turn makes the utilization of such hot water a challenge, which traditionally is dealt with by installing large heat accumulators for hot water production storage and utilization at multiple temperature levels¹⁴. We decided to

share our findings of an analysis performed on a particular chips cooking process that addressed the difficulties of heat recovery from such process, with the aims:

- to analyze the existing process in terms of existing heat recovery systems and their efficiency;
- to propose measures for smoothing the peaks in hot water production and minimizing its overflow to water tank with lower temperature, without the need for new heat storage capacity;
- to test the proposed measures with respect to their impact on level control ability in black liquor tanks and on increasing and stabilizing heat flux available at hot water level which enables its efficient utilization for steam saving purposes.

Case study

The object of our study is a part of black liquor storage tank farm coupled with hot water system for heat recovery located in a paper mill in Slovakia, presented in Figures 1 and 2. Tanks T1 and T2 store excess spent black liquor from batch digesters. This liquor has to be cooled down from around 100 to 120 °C to around 90 °C in heat exchangers HE1, 2 which use cooling water to produce hot water. The cooled down black liquor is stored in tank T3 before being pumped to Evaporation plant. The tank 4 stores washing liquor that has been cooled down in heat exchanger HX3 by warm water. Due to cyclical nature of batch wood chips digesting, flows of black liquor to tanks T1,2 vary considerably and so do also the flows of black liquor through HE1, 2. In order to meet the very changeable cooling duty, cooling water flow to these coolers varies in a very broad interval. Heat exchanger HE3 on the other hand operates without significant heat duty changes. Hot water produced in HE1, 2 represents the majority of overall hot water inlet to hot water tank A as can be seen in Figure 2. The limited hot water tank capacity together with quite rigid water level control does not allow for effective dampening of produced hot water peaks compared with more or less stable hot water consumption; thus hot water excess is periodically dumped into warm water tank B. There is constant excess of water in tank B, thus a part of it is sent to cooling towers, where around 7 MW heat are released to atmosphere. Thus it can be stated that warm water dumping from tank A to tank B worsens this situation further and represents additional heat loss from this heat recovery system. Flattening out the peaks in hot water production would allow for new stable hot water consumer plug in into the heat recovery system, leading to water steam saving and thus to marginal fuel (natural gas) saving in the end.

Figure 1. Schematic depiction of the analyzed part of black liquor tank farm. HE = heat exchanger; T =(storage) tank.

Figure 2. Schematic depiction of the existing warm and hot water system. Heat exchangers B, C are identical with HE1, 2 in Figure 1. A, B, C – most likely reasons for water level fluctuations in Water tank A.

Our efforts thus focused on two main tasks:

- testing possibilities for flattening peaks in black liquor release from storage tanks T1,2 by adopting improved stepwise level control instead of the current nearly ON/OFF control in very narrow black liquor level range
- implementing a new 70 and 50 °C water mixing possibility at the inlet of HE1, 2 to ensure less changeable hot water production and utilizing part of the 70 °C warm water sent to cooling towers, instead of fresh 50 °C cooling water, thus improving heat recuperation in the system

Calculation procedure incorporated:

- estimation of overall heat transfer coefficient dependence on black liquor flow rate
- development and testing of new level control strategies in tanks T1,2, resulting in less changeable black liquor flows through HE1,2 but avoiding strong fluctuations in black liquor level in T1,2.
- accommodating inlet cooling water temperature to match the adjusted HE1, 2 cooling duties due to adjusted black liquor flows that led to overall heat transfer coefficients and required heat transfer driving force adjustment as well
- comparison of cumulative heat surplus in produced hot water in original case and under adjusted conditions for a 48 hour-lasting testing period

Results and discussion

Material and energy balances of the system under study yielded trends depicted in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 illustrates the dependence of water level in tank A evolution and hot water production – In the initial phase of the depicted time period the elevated hot water production in HE1 and HE2 led to increased hot water level values in tank A. This however decreases gradually, not only because of somewhat decreased hot water production but also due to water dumping from tank A to tank B. The second half of the depicted period corroborates this as both water production and its level in tank A stabilized at lower values than at the beginning of the period. Repeated water dumping can though still be observed. After proposed changes implementation, one sees that hot water production increased generally and also fluctuates less than in the original case. This creates space for surplus hot water utilization in adjacent units: either in Washing and Bleaching units or as heat carrier for enhanced boiler feedwater preheat in the boiler house. In all cases this will lead to low pressure steam saving.

Figure 3. Trends of hot water production in HE1 + HE2 in original case and after implementing proposed changes; water level in tank A in original case – part of the testing 48 h period.

Plant operators were concerned about black liquor level fluctuations in case of proposed changes implementation. Material balance evolution of black liquor tanks has therefore been simulated to test the robustness of proposed level control changes against very high or very low black liquor levels. The comparison of those process parameters in original case and in the case after level control adjustment is shown in Figure 4. It can be seen that the levels in both tanks follow very similar trends in both cases with no significant increase in their fluctuations over time. Both existing and proposed level regulation strives to push them towards 50 %, which provides both regulation comfort for plant operators as well as sufficient black liquor buffer for unforeseen accidents.

Figure 4. Black liquor level evolution in tanks T1, 2 during a part of the testing 48 h period – original trends and trends calculated from tank material balance after proposed level regulation changes implementation.

Combined material and heat balance of the system allowed for benefit estimation of proposed system control and layout changes. Calculations confirmed that with adjusted system the cumulative 48 hour heat duty of both heat exchangers has been by 15 MWh higher than in the original case. Benefit estimation reflects the fact that heat duty of HE1 , 2, serving to raise the temperature of cooling water to that in tank B is considered “lost” because of continuous water excess in that tank. Thus only the valuable heat duty raising the water temperature above that in tank B has been summed up and compared for original case and case after system adjustment – it represents roughly 40 to 50 % of the total cumulated heat exchangers duty. Total cumulated valuable heat duty during the testing period was 267 MWh for original case while for the case after system adjustment it increased

to 346 MWh (= +20 %). Taking into account the testing period length and the difference in cumulative 48 hour heat duty we finally could arrive at the resulting average benefit of 1.5 MW. Considering heat price between 3 and 10 euro/GJ this corresponds to saving potential of 140 to 450 ths. euro/year. This value can be further increased when considering the resulting reduction of hot water dumping from tank A to tank B as well as reduction of water surplus in tank B that is sent to cooling towers. Estimation of this contribution to the total benefit is however out of the scope of this paper.

Conclusions

Efficient heat recuperation from cyclical and batch processes puts additional strain on process control compared to continuous processes. Too rigid level control in the capacity items (tanks) that are inevitably present in such systems can lead to propagation of heat carriers flow changeability downstream and thus to troubles in heat recuperation from hot to cold media. Our study has confirmed that a slight ease in level regulation strategy of hot medium storage tanks coupled with addition of cold medium temperature control can lead to significant heat recuperation to hot water potential exploitation increase. The extra produced heat in hot water can further be utilized in other part of pulp and paper production process to replace process stream heating with steam or for boiler feedwater preheating to decrease steam consumption in deaerators.

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